

THE VALUE OF WATERCOLOR AND GOUACHE MATERIAL IN THE TECHNIQUE OF WATER-BASED PAINT

Yunusaliev M.T.

Senior Lecturer, Department of Fine Arts, Faculty of Arts, Fergana State University

godirjon060858@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8335602>

Abstract. *Observing the process of students performing practical classes and independent study tasks in watercolor, reacting to the technological mistakes they made, I inform you that most students are watercolorists due to the fact that they did not feel a subtle difference in the technological aspects of the properties of gouache, the transparency property of watercolor in their work was disrupted. Colors are washed out, causing much of the work to be washed out. It turned out that they do not have full practical experience and knowledge about the types of watercolors and their characteristics. It is clear that they do not have enough experience and skills in this matter. With this in mind, below, a number of actions that students must strictly follow during practical training, as well as some theoretical aspects of the characteristics of watercolor and gouache paints in watercolor related to this topic, as well as some theoretical aspects of their working techniques, were given to students. To overcome the above problem, it is very important to constantly create alternating sketches in watercolor and gouache, in which watercolor is applied in a thin layer, and gouache. To work with a thick layer, the student is required to set a certain time. Only then will students gain some experience and be free from the above errors and shortcomings. As a result, they will gain practical knowledge and skills on this topic. This article presents an analysis of options for solving a problem situation regarding the differences between watercolors and gouache and the features of the technique of working with them.*

Keywords: *Watercolor, gouache, watercolor, torchon, technology, durable, technical method, painting, study, graphics, transparent, lessing, layered method, specific order, standard, feature, knowledge, experience, skill, methodology, analysis, type, easel painting, repair, exhibition, exposition, blur, color, creativity.*

INTRODUCTION.

It is appropriate to recall the opinion of Abu Nasr al-Farabi in the chapter on acquiring a profession:

"... Whoever has the virtue of discovering the most beautiful and useful thing, if what he discovers really corresponds to his desire and the desire of another person, or if there is a suspicion that it corresponds to the desire of others, then the discovered or created thing is really good and useful ". This idea is in the heart of every master.

Watercolor is a water-based paint, a type of painting done with water. Watercolor has been known since ancient times. Watercolor was also used in Egyptian papyri, Movaraunakhr mojaz (miniature) artwork, and Byzantine miniatures. Durer's watercolors have been known since the Middle Ages. During the Renaissance, watercolor was often used to sketch frescoes and easel paintings.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS.

Watercolor paintings by Bekhzod, Raphael, Rubens and other artists have survived to this day. Sadykbek Afshari, an Azerbaijani miniaturist and master who worked in the 12th century, writes about water-based paints in the history of his experiments: "If you make water-based paints with less glue, then when the paint dries, this color will turn out to pour out if you add too much glue , the paint will dry and the glue will come to the surface. So you need to find the norm."

In the book "Decoration of Manuscript Books" (XIII-XVIII centuries), Sadikbek further states: "If someone touches your work with an oily hand, you should gradually wash it off with bone glue, and when it dries, paint it again with the same paint. Smooth it out after dry.

Mir Imad Kazvin, master of the manuscript of the XVI-XVII centuries, writes in his book *Etiquette-Mashk* that there are other ways to remove grease stains:

"Take a little quicklime and sprinkle it on the surface of the soiled paper, put clean white paper on top of it and press it with a flat stone, and you will see that after a while the soiled place will return to its original state."

From them we know that the peoples of Central Asia have been dealing with water-based paints since ancient times, but due to a misinterpretation of religious beliefs, the number of followers of painting has decreased.

Watercolor first became an independent type of painting in England in the 17th century, and then in other European countries from the beginning of the 19th century.

Watercolor painting has very rich traditions in Russia. It was formed in Russia in the 18th century. At the beginning of the 19th century, it received great development in the work of A. A. Ivanov, K. I. Brubel and Fedotov.

In 1880, the first "Society of Watercolor Artists" was founded in Russia. This society annually holds exhibitions of watercolor artists. The great masters of Russian painting, such as I. E. Repin, I. Surikov, A. Serov, M. A. Vrubel, I. Levitan, created masterpieces of watercolor painting in various genres of art.

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, there were many creative movements in watercolor painting, each of which had a positive impact on the development of the Russian watercolor school. In our time, watercolor is an independent well-developed raw material. Today, most Uzbek artists create works of art in watercolor.

"Watercolor should teach the eye to see colors correctly, the hand to draw correctly and boldly with a brush, and the mind to calculate and deeply understand the laws of color," said P. P. Chistyakov.

RESULTS.

In the first year, the study of painting begins with watercolors. To work with watercolors, Torchon paper or waterproof and durable clean white paper is used, which is tightly applied to the tablet.

Practice sessions are usually 60x80 cm paper size. The paper should be stiff, as mentioned above, and should be able to withstand multiple coats of water-based paint, as well as not swell when washed. Thin paper that absorbs water is not suitable for long-term watercolor painting. Currently, this is "Torshon", which is produced specifically for watercolor painting.

Watercolor brushes should be soft and have sharp tips when immersed in water. Such brushes are made from the wool of the column. Watercolor paints dissolve well in water. This state gives it a special clarity and transparency when treated with a thin layer of water. If the surface of the paper is given a thick and dark color, the watercolor will lose its character.

Another problem with watercolor is the application of several layers of watercolor paint and subsequent correction. Therefore, it must be carried out strictly in a certain order. First, a few light colors are given and they remain open. Then gradually darker colors begin to appear. In order not to make corrections, the image must be clearly drawn and the work done carefully. It is necessary to try very accurately to apply paint to light areas. To determine the main colors of the work, it is advisable to first sketch it in a smaller size. Such a sketch helps in long-term work to find shades of color and decide on the paints used (**Figure-1**).

For the methodical implementation of long work processes in watercolor, the glazing (glazing) method is used. That is, at a certain stage of the work, when it has dried, in order to summarize the colors of some parts of the image, to give a thin layer of paint of a diluted pale color. Several precise color tones can be achieved by varnishing, in which several layers of dry paint are applied on top of each other, then skillfully applied in a thin layer in a general manner. Then unique color nuances appear in some parts of the image, which creates spatiality of the image, as a result, it becomes easier to control colors. And in this way you can find unique colors. Do not mix more than three types of paint to avoid paint contamination.

Figure-1

In this case, the Lesserovka method helps. But there are special rules for using glazing. The Lesserovka method is based on the transparency of paints, due to this transparency they are visible to the bottom. This feeling enhances the colors. Lesserovka is a generalizing method of color combination, full of bright reflections, it is especially widely used when depicting soft space, a plan in outdoor nature scenes.

DISCUSSION.

In the course of working on an etude, sometimes you have to erase some details or soften the color. Then most artists use a soft sponge. In such cases, it is best to use a soft brush, large in size, intended for watercolor (from squirrel wool), if possible. However, corrections should be treated very carefully, because, while maintaining the freshness and accuracy of the watercolor work, it is necessary not to damage the clarity and transparency of the paint layer. Watercolor works are so beautiful that they require the utmost precision and care even in details.

The image of the shape of large objects requires the utmost accuracy of artistic imagination and the utmost accuracy of color. Details should be light, they should come out clearly and reliably (**Figure-1**). Only then will it correspond to the artistic effect of the image. It is necessary to work with watercolor once and try to do the work without errors, then corrections are impossible. Otherwise, the corrected areas will spoil the quality of the work.

The technical method of segmentation is brush painting. In addition to the color of the brush, you should pay attention to its direction. A thin line is used to more clearly emphasize the shape. It is applied to the sharp end of the brush, with which small details of the image are drawn. For short-term sketches in watercolor, it is better to use the “wet work” method. The work done in this way is very interesting, and the painting effect is high. This method is based on the rule of

connecting one layer of paint to another layer of paint and embodies the brilliance of subtle colors of paints. The "wet work" method in watercolor is a rule of thumb combined with fast work and a good sense of color.

A good knowledge of the methods and rules of watercolor work is the key to success. It is a pleasure to work with watercolor, and its flicker is a sign that the artist's face is open. In the watercolor method, it is not easy to work out the details of the image. It requires the accuracy of artistic imagination, thoroughness of color, excellent understanding of the shape of three-dimensional objects.

An ancient painting method known as gouache, one of the types of watercolor, was first developed by the artist Paolo Pano, who created in the middle of the 16th century. In our time, it has become more popular, spreading as watercolor painting, where special gouache paints are used or gouache marks are added.

Figure-2

Gouache is a water-soluble paint, similar to watercolor, but it is a type of paint that is not transparent but covered in thick layers. Almost like oil paint. Unsuccessful areas can be repainted. But due to the chalk added to the gouache composition as a filler, when dried, the gouache changes its color and becomes pale. This feature of gouache creates great difficulties in the process of work. Therefore, it is necessary to find out exactly how pale it is. This task can be accomplished as a result of acquiring skills in the process of working with gouache. Gouache paint can be applied in liquid form, just like watercolor, but the gouache paste state requires special care, as a thick layer of paint tends to crack.

In addition, it is possible that the top layer in a pasty state is washed off and mixed with the lower layers. Gouache is easily washed off with water. Due to this property of gouache, it is absolutely impossible to apply thin paint to dry areas. In the process of working with gouache, you can use a wide range of color combinations to create impressive scenes. The properties of gouache can be fully demonstrated in decorative still lifes illuminated by light. It is effective to apply permanent paint to a form that does not take up much space and use it when things are not buried in this space. In such still lifes, the possibilities of gouache correspond to the landscape expressiveness of the work and the clear and precise fulfillment of the tasks of proportion. Also, gouache can be very productively used in theatrical painting, posters and graphics, folk art (**Figure 2**).

CONCLUSION.

Gouache can be usefully used mainly for sketching designs, and as a temporary decorative tool for decorative panels, as well as book graphics and folk art. In the process of training, we were once again convinced that reflection on the development and artistic level of teaching methods, along with practical exercises, is a requirement of our time. Of course, the colors and lines we create are not always decorative, only some of them can meet this requirement. Design students create various interior design sketches in course projects. If we teach them a wide range of artistic requests, they will surely try to discover new sides of the creative process. Based on this goal, students should learn when, how, and how to apply the color balance of watercolors and gouache paints when working in water-based paint. Otherwise, it is impossible to succeed in painting with

water-based paint. Accordingly, the student must always remember that the result of the work will be known during the demonstration.

REFERENCES

1. Р.Ш. Халилов. Учебное пособие «АКВАРЕЛЬ» ТАШКЕНТ 2009 г. (5-16 betlar)
2. R. Xudoyberganov. Rangshunoslik asoslari-Toshkent. G'.G'ulom nomida-gi nashriyotmatbaa ijodiy uyushmasi. 2006.
3. Sohibov, R. (2022). RANGLARNING ASOSIY XUSUSIYATLARI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 234-238.
4. Nodirjon, M., Abdusalom, M., & Ozodbek, S. (2021). TECHNOLOGIES OF TEACHING FINE ARTS WITH MODERN METHODS.
5. Ахмедова, Н. Э. (2022). МЎЪЖАЗ САНЪАТНИНГ БЕТАКРОР НАФОСАТ ОЛАМИ. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 125-130.
6. Sulaymanova, S. B. Q. (2022). BADIY OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARDA TASVIRIY SAN'AT FANINI O'QITISHGA BO'LGAN EHTIYOJNING OSHISHI VA UNING BUGUNGI HOLATI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 89-96.
7. Сулайманова, С. Б. К. (2022). BADIY TA'LIMDA TALABALARNI O'QITISHDA SAMARALI DIDAKTIK PRINSIPLARDAN FOYDALANISH USULLARI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 143-150.
8. Nazokat, A., Ibrokhim, Y., & Makhpuzakhon, A. (2021). FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF FINE ARTS.
9. Nazokat, A. (2021). Means of Ensuring the Integrity of the Image and Writing in the Performance of Visual Advertising.
10. Ахмедова, Н. Э. (2022). МЎЪЖАЗ САНЪАТНИНГ БЕТАКРОР НАФОСАТ ОЛАМИ. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 125-130.
11. Сулайманова, С. Б. К. (2022). BADIY TA'LIMDA TALABALARNI O'QITISHDA SAMARALI DIDAKTIK PRINSIPLARDAN FOYDALANISH USULLARI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 143-150.
12. Yuldashev, I. (2022). BORLIQNI IDROK ETISH VA TASVIRLASHGA DOIR DASTLABKI MA'LUMOTLAR HAMDA ULARNI XARAKTERLI JIHATLARI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 9-15.
13. A'zamjonov, A. A. Z. (2022). UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA TASVIRIY SAN'AT FANINI O'QITISHGA INNOVATSION YONDASHUV YO'LLARI MAVZUSI BO'YICHA AMALIY ISHLANMA. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 56-60.
14. Barchinoy, K., Sevarakhon, S., & Mukhammadkodir, Y. (2021). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FINE ARTS AND DRAWING AT SCHOOL.
15. БМ Курбанова, М Юнусалиев, Н Арзиева. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕХНИКИ: АКВАРЕЛЬ, МАСЛО И ГУАШЬ Research Focus 1 (2), 319-325
16. A'zamjonov, A., & Hamdamov, K. H. (2022). TASVIRIY SAN'AT MASHG'ULOTLARI MAZMUNINING DAVLAT TA'LIM STANDARTLARI BILAN BOG'LIQLIGI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(10-2), 71-77.

17. Boboyeva, Z. A., & Mo'Minova, D. B. Q. (2022). ALABALARNING KREATIVLIK QOBILİYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 221-233.

Internet:

[www. wikihow.com](http://www.wikihow.com)

[www. helenstrom.blogspot.com](http://www.helenstrom.blogspot.com)

[www. thesmartteacher.com](http://www.thesmartteacher.com)

[www. crayola.com](http://www.crayola.com)

[www. ziyonet.uz](http://www.ziyonet.uz)